

EVAGUIDE

Horizon 2020 Programme

Security Management Platform for enhanced situation awareness and real-time adaptive evacuation strategies for large venues for sports and entertainment

EVAGUIDE PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL AND BRANDING

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Abbreviations

EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
FTI	Fast Track Innovation
WP	Work Package
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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Executive Summary

The project focuses on the development of a ready-for-market product that will integrate all subsystems (core, mobile platform, crowd simulation algorithm etc) into a commercial evaguide platform (TRL8).

The main objective of T4.1 “evaguide branding and promo material”, is to create the evaGuide Brand that will be aligned with the vision of the project’s new joint venture, aiming to exploit the evaGuide business case.

A Brand - “is a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers, and to differentiate them from those of competitors¹”. The “branding” procedure will enable the introduction of the evaguide system to the evacuation solutions landscape and elaborate a customized market approach, which can support the perspective of commercializing the platform to potential end-users.

The deliverable aims to establish systematic channels and means for disseminating the project objectives, activities, progress and technological outcomes to the evaGuide stakeholders. This includes the creation of all necessary printed and mainly digital material (logo, leaflets, brochures, videos, website, social presence), in order to attract more end-users (stadium operators).

Key role in these approach plays the project’s website, developed in view of presenting project’s results, including project objectives and background, significant achievements, technology news, consortium contacts, publications, presentations, etc. The website will be maintained and updated in a regular basis during the project lifetime.

¹ David A. Aaker, “Building Strong Brands”, New York: The Free Press, 1996

1 Introduction

This document is focused on presenting the developed evaGuide branding and promotional material for the evaguide project and it is divided into three (3) main parts.

- The first part presents the branding activities based on the evaGuide vision, mission and values. Our primary target is to create a uniquely identified brand that will be connected directly with the evaGuide project especially when the project ends. Several attempts are also presented together with a thorough description of our identity logo.
- The second part refers to the project website, presenting a detailed description of the content and features. The website also aims to provide access to news, updates and events related to the developments of the evaGuide project, and will thus be updated regularly during the project duration. The site is addressed to everyone who is interested in the project (from specialised scientists to the general public, as well as other consortiums). By providing the contact details of the coordinating organisations, the visitor may request further details or send comments/proposals for further improvements.
- The third part reviews the project's social media presence. Our focus is on social media channels that considered highly professional, such as Twitter and LinkedIn. Following the guidelines of the EC regarding communication activities, we designed our social media channels with the main goal to attract visitors and gain the attention of the wide audience.

2 evaGuide brand identity

The development of the brand for the evaGuide project was one of the main topics discussed in the Kick-Off meeting, since it is one of the most important issues in every ambitious project. It is very common for the brand essence to evolve over the lifetime of a project since it is a distillation of its vision and values. The project full name, “Security management platform for enhanced situation awareness and real-time adaptive evacuation strategies for large venues for sports and entertainment”, can act as a self-explanatory tagline but our intention is to shorten it and make it focused in our vision once the project progresses and reaches a certain maturity level.

2.1 evaGuide vision

The evaGuide project envisions a safer and more comfortable experience for people in large venues like the stadia around the world. Safer, in the case where an unpredicted event takes place, all the people in the stadium will have a complete picture of how they will evacuate the venue and comfortable, since the spectators will only have to worry for their team’s performance and not their safety.

2.2 evaGuide mission

The evaGuide project will change the way security companies operate within large venues for sports and entertainment by providing a novel Security Management Platform for enhanced situation awareness and real-time adaptive evacuation strategies.

2.3 evaGuide values

Brand values are the core values that are vital to the realization of the brand. To ensure the brand is delivered in a consistent way, its values have to be aligned with the brand vision. The evaGuide values are:

- Collaborate to have a real impact on people’s safety and quality of life;
- Innovate in order to support improvement and continuous growth; and
- Commit to the project vision

2.4 Target groups

From the early beginning of the project, the consortium identified the targeted audience and thus the potential customers that are critical to the success of the project. An indicative (although abstract) list was created using an analytical approach in order to identify the target groups of potential customers as it can be seen in Table 1: Target groups and communication means Table 1 below. Apart from the groups of people that have a strong interest in evaGuide, we also describe the way they potentially perceive our project and its foreseen outcomes together with the appropriate communication effort and mean to approach them. During the project’s lifespan, this list will be enlarged and refined according to the results achieved and based on our experience gained through the interaction with people that belong to these categories.

Table 1: Target groups and communication means

	Target audience	Their perception of evaGuide	Ways to communicate
Audience 1	Stadium Operators	A system to enhance safety in cases of disaster phenomena and manmade	End-user workshops and ESMA network

		hazards that works together with their systems	
Audience 2	Safety and Security Operators Stewarts/ Stadia Security Companies	A system that helps them to be more useful and effective during evacuation processes.	End-user communication channels and workshops
Audience 3	Policy influencers Policy makers Organisations like National Fire Protection Association (NFPA)	A system that contributes to strengthening Europe’s ability to deal with situation awareness in large sport venues.	Consortium’s networks Information on the website e.g. current policies and developments in evacuation of large venues
Audience 4	Technical and Scientific community (civil engineers, architectures, electrical engineers, etc)	Using the latest technology to build safe and secure stadia	Conferences, technical workshops, liaison actions with other similar EU projects Website information Social Media
Audience 5	Wider audience	How technology helps to improve safety in large stadia	Website Social Media (Twitter and LinkedIn)

2.5 evaGuide Identity and logo

Figure 1: evaGuide logo in business cards

A project logo is considered its visual identity simplified into a single icon. Several versions of the evaGuide logo were created during the first months of the project, aiming at capturing the essence of our vision and convey the idea of creating safer venues for the people through innovative evacuation strategies. At the time of the writing of this deliverable, the focus of the consortium is on large sport venues, which clearly explains the stadium depicted in the evaGuide logo. In order to emphasize the evacuation process, we added a green arrow that represents the safe route for evacuating a stadium in case of emergency. The design principle that was followed, aims at creating a

logo that can be fully recognizable and instantly connected with the evaGuide project (and eventually product) in a unique way, even after the project ends, capturing the users’ attention and making easy for them to understand what our brand represents.

The visual elements of the logo are

- Distinct, since it easily stands out among other similar products;
- Memorable, since it draws the attention of the people;
- Flexible, so as to evolve together with the brand; and
- Cohesive, since each piece complements the brand identity.

Figure 2: evaGuide logo in t-shirts

The evaGuide logo is purely simplistic since it does not contain too many distractions for the eye, thus making it really easy to remember. The colours of the logo are only three, orange, violet and green. Two of them, green and orange, are light colours in an attempt to avoid negative connotations. The dark one, the violet, has been chosen in order to trigger the feeling of suppression that is met in crisis events and at the same time impose independence and high quality. In addition, all of the above mentioned colours reveal their great features once they are combined. Orange is a more subtle and cozy colour that creates the feeling of comfortness, violet inspires confidence and success and green

dictates serenity and active decision-making.

As part of the design process, we also considered the way the logo appears among other material so as it looks perfect on posters, t-shirts and books or leaflets (Figures 1, 2, 3). An important aspect of the logo design was the approach we followed by avoiding trendy icons, since it will not last through time and classic ones, since it might also have been used by other similar products in the previous years.

Concluding this section, it is worth mentioning that the fully fleshed out brand strategy we have followed provided the blueprint upon which the logo was designed. Insight and intuition were the main advantages the evaGuide consortium used for creating a logo that it will have great impact in the world and the EU citizens. Our overall goal was to convey the project purpose to the wide audience and gain visibility for future commercial activities. evaGuide was set for success which is reflected in our brand values and voice whereas the visual design of our logo works in tandem with these key elements.

Figure 3: evaGuide logo in books

2.5.1 Proposed logos

For the development of the logo of evaGuide, several approaches were created until reaching the one that was selected by the consortium. For reasons of completeness, we include in the figure below some of our initial drafts.

Figure 4: evaGuide draft logos

3 evaGuide website

The evaGuide website was developed using state-of-the-art technologies, such as HTML5, JavaScript and it is based on a responsive design, allowing its access from a wide variety of browsers and devices (PCs, smartphones and tablets).

The website is available under the following link <http://www.evaguide.eu>.

3.1 Website structure

The horizontal, “static” menu of the website is presented in the figure below:

The menu structure is comprised by the below central pages:

- Home
- Project
- Consortium
- Downloads
- News
- Contact Us

At the bottom of every page of the site, the EU emblem followed by the description that the project (GA no 831154) has received funding from the EU under the H2020 programme, is placed.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under grant agreement no 831154.

A detailed presentation of the contents of the above mentioned central pages follows.

3.1.1 Home page

The first page of the site is the Home page, depicted in the figure below. It works as a welcome page, informing the visitors about the project scope and goals, including also a “learn more” link to an overview page with extra information about the project.

The page consists of a main horizontal menu, as presented and described above, followed by relevant with the project images/video and an additional strip menu with links to the latest project news, the consortium and objectives. Both the main upper menu with the project logo and the EC contribution with the social media icons at the bottom, appear in all pages of the website.

At the end of the first page, contact information of the project coordinator (Telesto Technologies) is provided, giving the opportunity to any interested party for further interaction with the project consortium.

Figure 5 – Home page

3.1.2 Project

This page illustrates the aim of the project, to whom it may refer, the goals and basic outcomes. Background details about the project such as the GA number, the duration, the total cost etc are also provided.

Figure 6 – Project main page

The “project” page includes four (4) sub-pages with the following content:

- Concept
- Objectives
- Impact
- WP structure

which are presented in the following paragraphs.

3.1.2.1 Concept

For further understanding the concept of the project, the visitor will be informed about the environment of the project, the need, the opportunity, the limitations and technological/ operatinal challenges that led to the subission of the proposal.

Figure 7 – Project concept

3.1.2.2 Objectives

The project objectives are categorized according to three pillars: Technical Excellence, User Adoption and Financial Sustainability as presented in the relevant sub-page below.

The project objectives are categorized according to three pillars: Technical Excellence, User Adoption and Financial Sustainability. For every objective, relevant tasks and deliverables have been defined accompanied by deadlines for delivery.

Technical Excellence

- Objective 1.1:** Develop to the ready-for-market level, the evaGuide Mobile Application, evaGuide Core and Crowd Modeling algorithms (Task T11-T12, Deliverables D11-D18, milestone fulfilled by M14)
- Objective 1.2:** Integrate the individual subsystems into one common evaGuide platform that supports the complete lifecycle of all the evacuation (modeling, simulation, planning, including risk identification and assessment, training, alerting, simulation and supporting exercises), all day-to-day operations and finally all real-time evacuation support (Task T13-D19, on M15)
- Objective 1.3:** Exhaustively test and demonstrate (see Task T14 description) the integrated evaGuide platform and establish, within the project lifetime, an operational demonstrator in one European stadium that represents the fully operational capabilities of the system (Task T14, D18, D20, D21, D22, on M15-M18)

User Adoption

- Objective 2.1:** Validate the concept against IFA (International Federation of Football Associations) and UEFA (Union European of Football Associations) regulatory frameworks, given the support of the European Stadium and Safety Management Association (ESSEMA) to ensure that evaGuide supports operational requirements for stadium evacuation (Task T12, D14, finally delivered on M14)
- Objective 2.2:** Validate the evaGuide concept against ethical, legal and societal aspects to ensure that evaGuide features are in compliance with the above frameworks (Task T11, D13 and D11, finally delivered on M14)
- Objective 2.3:** Through the support of ESSEMA achieve MoU with other early adopters of the evaGuide platform (Task T12, D14 on M14)
- Objective 2.4:** Offer unique mobile-based content that will combine evaGuide features for safety, convenience and venue-specific content to the spectators of the stadium, to ensure the early adoption of users (Task T12, D13 and D15 on M12 and M14 respectively)
- Objective 2.5:** Review and contribute to existing standardisation effort such as the ISO/TC 293 – Societal Security with respect to facility evacuation processes (special focus on ISO 16336 Societal Security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning), the EN/TC 191 on 'Societal & Citizen Security', the ETSI 3GPP/5G, the ENXCP initiatives etc (Task T11, D17 on M14)
- Objective 2.6:** Establish methodologies and tools to ensure that the best practices and technologies are made aware to the market (Task T12, D14 and D15, finally delivered but final revision M14)

Business Sustainability

- Objective 3.1:** Provide the economic, 7 years of the business and technical hypothesis of the evaGuide concept in order to minimize the investment risk and maximise potential profit after the end of the proposed project (Task T11, Deliverables D14 and D12, reached on M14 and M14 respectively)
- Objective 3.2:** Provide all necessary monetization mechanisms (licensing schemes, pricing strategy) which including the establishment of a "virtual" company within the project duration, which will ensure the rapid joint venture company establishment and revenues generation immediately after the end of the project (Task T11, Deliverable D15 on M14)
- Objective 3.3:** Provide a realistic business plan and scale-up strategy of the project (Task T12, D14 on M14)

The project outcome: A fully functional evaGuide platform (ready-to-use) delivered for operational use by one stadium (most probably one of the ESSEMA member clubs, selected on M14). The demonstrator will perform according to the adopted requirements defined by ESSEMA and the stakeholders involved (finalized on M14), will be fully integrated by M14 and tested (M14), ready to be commercially executed by the new commercialization "vehicle" (contract M14)

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The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 831154

Figure 8 – Project objectives

3.1.2.3 Impact

One of the most important issues to be considered in order to choose for the funding of a project, is the social, technological and economical impact that imposes to the society. evaGuide will increase the perception of security among citizens, especially in times where the threat of a terrorist attack in large crowded areas is considered as imminent. The impact of the project is described in the page below.

Figure 9 – Project impact

3.1.2.4 WP structure

evaGuide is a project that brings together a set of interdisciplinary WPs to yield the final congruent system prototype ready for pilot demonstration. The work is shared in six (6) work packages as shown below.

Figure 10 – Project WPs

3.1.3 Consortium

The consortium is composed of 4 partners: (1) Telesto Technologies (TEL), which has achieved the development of an enterprise mobile platform for the provision of location-based, personalised, safety-related information and improved situational awareness and will integrate its system with the IoT platform from (2) EXUS to adapt to the needs of large facilities safety. (3) CDI offers specialist crowd simulation development and (4) ESSMA provides business intelligence and domain expertise, facilitating the early adoption of the envisaged product.

Consortium details are described in the following figure. A hyperlink to the member's official website is applied by pressing the corresponding web address or the partner's logo.

Figure 11 – Project consortium

3.1.4 Downloads

The “download page” includes sub-pages with the following content:

- Deliverables
- Presentations
- Dissemination
- Publications

which are presented below.

The sub-pages contain links to downloading the evaGuide's relevant material (e.g. leaflets, brochures), papers, presentations, multimedia files and public deliverables and will be continuously updated during the project duration.

Figure 12 – Downloads main page

3.1.4.1 Presentations

In this page general, public presentations are provided which describe the project's technical progress, results, dissemination activities and events.

Figure 13 – Project presentations

3.1.4.2 Dissemination

This section will include various dissemination material such as the logo, leaflets, articles, posters, multimedia material etc.

For the time being, the page is empty since the project is in its starting phase.

3.1.4.3 Deliverables

The page presents the deliverable's list, aiming to inform the visitors about the work to be delivered. The deliverables list include the code name of the deliverable, the title, the delivery date and the dissemination level. The public (PU) deliverables will be available for download for any interested party.

3.1.5 News

One of the most important communication tool to disseminate the project’s results are the news page, that shows all the activities of the project and the actual progress of the project’s objectives, goals and outcomes.

Figure 16 – project news

3.1.6 Contact us

The contact information is presented in the end of the Home page, but there is also a separate link to the main menu bar that leads to the same information for the project coordinator.

Figure 17 – Contact Us

By selecting find us on map, the address of the project coordinator is depicted on map.

Figure 18 – Contact address

3.2 Website smartphone compatible view

The site has been designed in a way that can be viewed by any mobile device like smartphone or tablet. A collection of screenshots from various pages is depicted below.

Figure 19 – Website smartphone compatible view

4 evaGuide social media presence

It is without doubt that the European Commission wants to be transparent with the EU citizens and assist them in understanding what the so-called “EU membership fees” bring to their lives. In evaGuide project, strong emphasis is put on the communication activities that will be performed within the project’s lifespan in order to raise awareness of the main outcomes of the project and promote its activities. Despite the contractual obligation that every H2020 project has regarding communication activities, we strongly believe that through various communication channels, we will create market demand for our envisioned product, promote our project activities, network with other projects in a similar field and exchange know-how or even receive invaluable feedback by experts in the field of safety.

The first question to be answered for a successful communication strategy is who is interested to our project and thus our product, since there is an imperative need to identify the audience for the evaGuide project. The next step is to take advantage of all the available tools to reach and multiply our audiences, such as the website and the social media and linked them together, so as anyone interested in the project can easily find all the available information.

Communication through social media is an interactive and rapid way to reach the targeted audience and at the same time, gain visibility, thus maximizing the impact of the project results. evaGuide project will have a strong presence in Twitter and LinkedIn, since these two social media are the most suitable ones for the project purposes. Nevertheless, in case of additional foreseen benefits, the project will also expand its presence in additional social media such as YouTube, Facebook, etc.

The evaGuide social media channels have been created in order to reflect the project branding with each account targeting a diverse group of people according to the specificities of the abovementioned networks. They have been fully operational from the early beginning of the project aiming at increasing user participation and thus visibility and popularity. The social media accounts are also incorporated via “buttons” in our website page, at the bottom of the home page.

4.1 evaGuide in LinkedIn

The evaGuide landing page in LinkedIn can be seen in Figure 20 – evaGuide LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/evaguide-h2020-project/>). The design of this page follows the guidelines of the EC acknowledging the EU funding received for the evaGuide project. As it can be readily seen, besides the EU emblem, we have included a text stating that **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under grant agreement no 831154”** and a white strip with the logos of each consortium partner. A brief description with the main goals of the project has been added under the evaGuide logo together with hashtags related to our project so as become visible in more user communities. All the events, publications, news, photos, videos, campaigns and press releases will also be published here, redirecting the visitor/follower to our website for more information. It is worth pointing out that all our social media pages can be considered as a standalone version of our website but with minimal information included since they are more viral in terms of evolution and interaction.

Figure 20 – evaGuide LinkedIn page

4.2 evaGuide in Twitter

The same design principles (that we followed for LinkedIn) were followed for the Twitter account (https://twitter.com/evaGuide_H2020) with a few changes regarding the flexibility of this specific communication channel. We added more hashtags in our profile account trying to draw attention to specific domains related to our project. Twitter provides brief and fast communication with many users and it will be particularly useful for creating impact and reaching target audiences through campaigns that cover the participation of evaGuide in fairs and events, visual content (e.g., videos, pictures, etc.) of our activities and highlights of the project's results.

Since the interaction with other users and projects is real-time and sometimes responses are required, we “pinned” a specific tweet stating that [**@evaGuide_H2020 has received funding from the European Union's #H2020 for Research and Innovation under GA No. 831154. The content of this site reflect only the authors' view & the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information the website contains.**](#)

Figure 21 – evaGuide Twitter page